

Synthesis of pyrazole and pyrazole amidocobaloximes

A. Rajeshwar Rao, G. Gopinath, J. V. Madhuri and S. Satyanarayana*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007, India

E-mail : ssnisirasani@yahoo.com

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A series of cyano (ligand) cobaloximes have been prepared where, the ligand is pyrazole (Pz), 1-(acetamido)pyrazole (Apz), 1-(*N*-methylacetamido)pyrazole (MAPz), 1-(acetamido)-3,5-dimethylpyrazole (MADMPz). The complex $K[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)SCN]$ reacts with ethanolic solution of pyrazole or pyrazole amido ligands to form mixed ligand complexes. In all these complexes, the pyrazoles act as monodentate ligands and bind to Co^{III} through N-2 of pyrazole ring.

The bis(dimethyl glyoximato) Co^{III} system is generally known as cobaloximes and are ideal systems for structural comparisons^{1,2}. The four corrin ring equatorial N donors in B_{12} compounds are replaced by the four N atoms of a bis(dimethyl glyoximato) moiety in cobaloximes. This class of compounds has been the subject of intense study as models for $Vit.B_{12}$ chemistry with a wide range of functionalities^{3,4}. In the present work, cobalt complexes containing pyrazole and some of pyrazole amides as nitrogen donor ligands of general formula $[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)B]$ where D_2H_2 is dimethyl glyoxime and B = pyrazole (Pz), 3,5-dimethylpyrazole (DMPz), 1-(acetamido)pyrazole (APz), 1-(*N*-methylacetamido)pyrazole (MAPz), 1-(acetamido)-3,5-dimethyl pyrazole (ADMPz), 1-(*N*-methylacetamido)-3,5-dimethyl pyrazole (MADMPz) are synthesized and characterized. X-Ray crystallographic studies revealed that the pyrazole ligands coordinate to the metal ion through the unsubstituted *N*-2-(pyridine-nitrogen)⁵⁻⁷. Based on ν_{CN} it is concluded that $Co^{III} \rightarrow CN$ π bonding is increased with increasing the basicity of ligands *trans* to CN.

Results and discussion

The UV-visible spectral data of pyrazole and pyrazole amido cobaloximes are presented in Table 1.

The IR spectra of complexes in the solid state contain characteristic bands due to Co-N, C=N, N-O-H, N-O, C=N, ν_{N-H} and amide bands are assigned accordingly^{7,8}. There are three amide bands and the absorption bands in the region 1630–1640 cm^{-1} . The absorption bands in the region 1630–1690 cm^{-1} are generally assigned as amide-1 band due to ν_{CO} . Amide 2 and 3 bands have been assigned tentatively and are subjected to uncertainties owing to the presence of bending vibrations due to methyl groups absorbing strongly in the same region. The bands at 1555 (s),

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour	λ_{max}	Mol. cond** S. $cm^2 mol^{-1}$
$K[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)SCN]$	Red	273	80
$[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)Pz]$	Red	239	6
$[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)DMPz]$	Red	256	6
$[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)APz]$	Red	272	8
$[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)MAPz]$	Brown	276	8
$[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)ADMPz]$	Brown	263	10
$[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)MADMPz]$	Brown	258	12

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and Co analysis.

** In DMSO.

1440 (m) and 1035 (m) cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(C=C)$, $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N-N)$ of the pyrazole ring respectively. There are also other medium sharp bands appearing in the range 690–840 cm^{-1} due to out of plane ring deformation vibrations⁹⁻¹¹.

The IR spectral data indicates monodentate coordination of pyrazole amides via the N-2 of pyrazole. An appreciable positive shifts of $\nu(C=N)$ (15–40 cm^{-1}) and $\nu(N-N)$ (~20–30 cm^{-1}) modes of pyrazole ring in the IR spectra of above Co^{III} complexes compared with their corresponding free ligand band positions also support the above proposition that, N-2 of pyrazole is the binding site^{12,13}. The band around 450 cm^{-1} is due to $Co^{III} \rightarrow N$ of pyrazole. Appearance of this band confirms the coordination of pyrazole to Co^{III} .

In general CN^- is a better σ donor and a poorer π acceptor than CO. Thus the ν_{CN} of the complexes are higher¹¹ than the value for free CN^- . In the complexes studied CN stretching frequency of $K[(CN)Co(D_2H_2)SCN]$ is 2144 cm^{-1} . When SCN is replaced by pyrazole or substituted pyrazoles ν_{CN} is shifted to lower frequency 4–10 cm^{-1} .

Pyrazole and substituted pyrazoles are better donors than SCN as the donor capacity of the ligand *trans* to CN^- increases back donation from $\text{Co}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{CN}^-$ increases and CN^- stretching frequency decreases. Poulton *et al.*¹⁴ also observed the decreases in CO stretching frequency as the donor power of *trans* ligand is increased.

The starting material $\text{NH}_3\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{SCN}$ was characterised by elemental ^1H and ^{13}C NMR. The ^1H NMR of $\text{SCNCo}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{NH}_3$ gave signal at 2.217 and 2.673 corresponding to $(\text{CH}_3)_4$ and NH_3 protons respectively. Similarly ^{13}C NMR gave signals at 13.85 and 152.19 for $(\text{CH}_3)_4$ and C=N carbon. The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes gave well resolved absorptions corresponding to the ligands and equatorial methyl groups of D_2H_2 . The chemical shifts were found to be in the upfield order of H-4 > H-3 > H-5 for Pz, APz, and MAPz, a similar trend was reported for some of the related compounds such as 1-carbonamide pyrazoles¹⁵. Also a relative chemical shifts of the $-\text{CH}_3$ groups are found to be in the upfield order Me-3 > Me-5. A low field resonance for Me-5 is expected because of the anisotropy of the adjacent C=O bond¹⁵. There is an appreciable difference in the fields of absorption of Me (3) and Me (5), although small (~ 0.1 ppm) in the case of methyl groups, where the $-\text{CH}_2\text{CONHR}$ group is substituted at position-1 in all the ligands. The chemical shifts due to $-\text{CH}_2$ protons has been found to be sensitive with respect to substituents on amide nitrogen and varies in the order $-\text{NH}_2 > -\text{NHMe}$. Similarly, the resonances due to Me-5 in the compounds ADMPz and MADMPz are observed at lower field than those of Me-3 resonances. However, the

difference in chemical shifts between Me-3 and Me-5 are found to be small. All the ligands display sharp singlets due to $-\text{CH}_2$ protons in the range 4.50–4.72 ppm and the relative chemical shifts of these methylene groups are in the following order with respect to the substituents on the amidic nitrogen $-\text{NH}_2 > -\text{NHMe}$.

The resonances due to N- CH_3 protons of MAPz and MADMPz appear in each case as two singlets (appear more like doublet) and this may be due to splitting by the $-\text{NH}$ (amide) proton. The amide proton resonances are observed at sufficiently lower fields as broad singlets in all the compounds between 6.1 and 11.7 ppm.

The ^1H NMR spectra of all these complexes also support the monodentate coordination for the pyrazole and pyrazole amides. The spectrum exhibits bands due to H-3 (7.71 ppm), H-4 (6.35 ppm) and H-5 (7.22 ppm) of the pyrazole ring with a consistent upfield shift. This is expected as the pyrazole ring suffers some loss in its aromaticity due to the withdrawal of electron density from N-2 to Co^{III} and as a result of this the ring protons experience a higher shielding effect. In pyrazole ligand, three signals were observed corresponding to C-4 (6.35 ppm), C-3 (7.80 ppm), C-5 (7.91 ppm) and N-1 (11.70 ppm). When pyrazole coordinates to Co^{III} through N-2 of pyrazole ring, the C-3 and C-5 signals separates and gives two signals at 7.71 and 7.22 ppm respectively. The resonance due to H-4 occurs at δ 6.35 with a marginal upfield shift. In pyrazole amides, the resonances due to $-\text{CH}_2$ protons are found in a slightly upfield region and this can be explained on the basis of the reasons related to the loss of aromaticity discussed above for the ring pro-

Fig. 1. ^{13}C [^1H] NMR spectrum of $[^{13}\text{C}^{15}\text{NCo}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{Pz}]$ complex.

tons. In addition to the above signals these complexes exhibit a singlet at δ 2.30 ppm due to equatorial methyls.

The ^{13}C [^1H] NMR spectral data with probable assignments for all the carbon atoms present in the pyrazole and pyrazole amide ligands (Pz, DMPz, APz, MAPz, ADMPz and MADMPz, Fig. 1) show the ^{13}C chemical shift of $[(\text{CN})\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{Pz}]$ complex. The signals due to C-3, C-4 and C-5 are assigned easily¹⁶. The resonance due to C-3 and C-5 of pyrazole ring appears to be sensitive to the nature of the substituents at the 3 and 5 positions. The singlet resonances due to methylene carbons in the ligands also appear (2.0) to be dependent on the nature of the ring substituents at 3 and 5 positions, thus the corresponding singlet of ADMPz (50.97 ppm) with methyl substituent occur in the upfield region compared with the singlet of APz (53.78 ppm) with no substituents at C-3. The effect of substitution on the amide nitrogen can be clearly seen in the carbonyl carbon resonances. The other singlet resonance at 10.62 ppm corresponds to methyl carbon of ADMPz. In addition to these, in $[\text{CN}-\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{B}]$ complexes a singlet at 13.5 ppm corresponding to methyl groups of D_2H_2 and peak around 119 ppm corresponds to carbon signals of CN in the complex.

Experimental

Pyrazole, 3,5-dimethyl pyrazole, KCN (Sigma-Aldrich) and dimethyl glyoxime (B.D.H.) were used. Double-distilled water was used throughout the study.

^1H and ^{13}C NMR were recorded on Varian Gemini XL 200 JEOL, JNM-EX 90A FTNMR spectrometers, IR spectra on FTIR-1605 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on Uvikon-923 spectrophotometer. Microanalysis was performed on a Perkin Elmer-2380 instrument. A Digisun DI-909 conductivity bridge was used to determine the conductivities in water, methanol or DMSO by preparing 1×10^{-3} M solutions.

Preparation of $K[(\text{CN})\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)(\text{SCN})]$: It was synthesized¹⁷⁻¹⁹ by treating a suspension of $[\text{NH}_3\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)(\text{SCN})]$ (2.18 g, 5.86 mM) in 100 ml of ethanol with 0.382 g (5.86 mM) of KCN dissolved in minimum amount of water. This suspension was heated to 40–50° for 20 min by stirring, during which a dirty yellow suspension changed to red crystals of $K[(\text{CN})\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)(\text{SCN})]$ which was filtered, washed with methanol and ether and dried *in vacuo* (yield 92%).

Synthesis of pyrazole amido ligands :

Pyrazole amides were synthesized from the procedure available in the literature²⁰.

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of general formula $[(\text{CN})\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{B}]$:

The ligand B (2.4 mM) (B = Pz, DMPz, APz, MAPz, ADMPz and MADMPz) was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol or water. To this, an ethanolic solution of $K[(\text{CN})\text{Co}(\text{D}_2\text{H}_2)\text{SCN}]$ (0.485 mM) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 24 h by constant stirring while heating upto 70°. Ethanol was removed under reduced pressure and water was added to induce precipitation. The product was recrystallised from ethanol and water, washed with water, ethanol and ether, dried *in vacuo* (yield 75%).

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